

IMAGINE

**THEORETICAL PERSPECTIVES ON EU
CONSTITUTIONAL LAW**

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IMAGINE Working Paper No. 46

Abstract: This chapter, which will appear in the forthcoming *Research Handbook on EU Constitutional Law* (edited by Leonard Besselink, Nicola Lupo and Mattias Wendel), provides an overview of the development of EU constitutional theory - the field of scholarly inquiry concerned with the broader and deeper questions of the basic concepts of EU constitutional law, in particular the nature of the EU, its legal order and its various elements. It argues that while claims about the constitutional nature of the European integration project have been made since its early beginnings, a truly original constitutional theory of the EU emerged much later, coinciding with the establishment of the European University Institute and its first major project, *Integration through Law*, in the late 1970s. The chapter concludes with an overview of the main constitutional theories of the EU today, based on earlier research conducted as part of IMAGINE.

Keywords: EU constitutional theory, intellectual history of EU constitutionalism, integration through law

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IMAGINE has received funding from the European Research Council (ERC) under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme (grant agreement No 803163). More information can be found at <https://www.imagine-const.eu/>.

Theoretical Perspectives on EU Constitutional Law

Forthcoming in

Research Handbook on EU Constitutional Law

edited by

Leonard Besselink, Nicola Lupo and Mattias Wendel

(Edward Elgar)

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1. Introduction

While there are many (text)books on EU constitutional law today,¹ one can agree with Neil Walker (himself a distinguished constitutional theorist) that ‘theoretical exploration of the law and constitution of the EU is arguably less developed, less articulate, and less engaged within a common framework of debate than might be expected of a matter of such innovative significance’.²

In this chapter I set aside a non-trivial question of whether a theory of EU constitutional law is even possible (and if so, how such theory might look like).³ I assume that the field of scholarly inquiry that is usually so called concerns the more general and deeper questions dealing with the foundational concepts of EU constitutional law, especially the nature of the EU, its legal order, and its various elements. These would include e.g. the organisation of public power in the EU, the division of competences among the EU institutions and between the EU and its member states, the citizenship of the EU, the rights (and duties) of EU citizens, etc. To a large

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I would like to thank to the participants of the seminar at The Jean Monnet Center for International and Regional Economic Law & Justice, NYU School of Law (19 October 2023), and colleagues from *iCourts*, who provided generous and incisive comments at our summer retreat on 21 August 2023. I shall also acknowledge the great help I got from Vera Fritz with giving me access to her materials and giving valuable insights into the early period of European legal integration. Bill Davies, Morten Rasmussen, Päivi Leino-Sanberg and Michael Wilkinson also provided very helpful comments.

¹ Surely risking criticism by some colleagues for omitting their (favourite) one, I would mention particularly the textbook by Koen Lenaerts, the first edition of which was published in 1999 – as one of the first bearing such title (not an innocent choice, as I will explain in this chapter too): Koen Lenaerts K, Piet Van Nuffel PV and Robert Bray, *Constitutional Law of the European Union* (Sweet & Maxwell 1999).

² Neil Walker, ‘Legal and Constitutional Theory of the European Union’ in Paul Craig and Gráinne de Búrca (eds), *The Evolution of EU Law* 3rd Edition (Oxford University Press 2021), 90-122, 90.

³ See Jan Komárek, ‘Constitutional Theory of the EU as Play’, draft.

extent, the table of contents of this *Handbook* gives a basic idea of what EU constitutional theory can be theorizing. The important feature of a theory consists in its ambition to analyse and *understand* the constitution rather than to make it and advocate for it. Only then, I believe, is it possible to demarcate the field of “constitutional *theory*” from other sorts of scholarly inquiry into constitutional law.⁴

Compared to its member states, the EU (and the Communities which preceded it) has always suffered from an “identity question”: what sort of entity is it and does it have a constitution? This has sometimes made the distinction between theoretical and other (more practice-oriented) scholarship on EU law particularly blurred, or, as I will argue in this chapter, had kept constitutional theory of European integration rather under-developed for many years. As will be seen throughout the chapter, constitutional *theory* of the EU came much later after the claims about the constitutional nature of the whole integration project were made by the early protagonists, such as Walter Hallstein or Pierre Pescatore. In this respect this chapter departs from the narrative provided especially by the “new legal historians” in their invaluable work on the history of European law.

The “identity question”, which had once occupied relatively closed circles of legal elites came to the forefront in the 1990s, with the attempt to make the Union explicitly “federal” by the Maastricht Treaty at the beginning of the 1990s. The “f-word” was dropped, similarly as the “c-word” after the failure of an explicitly constitutional document (called ambiguously “Treaty Establishing a Constitution of Europe”) in 2005.⁵

Notwithstanding these ‘semantic struggles’,⁶ we can identify several stages of EU constitutional theory.⁷ The first opens with the initial attempts by lawyers-politicians (and lawyers-diplomats) to make the European Communities, founded by international treaties, “constitutional”. As will be seen in Part 2 of this chapter, those who argued for the Community law’s constitutional nature in this early period (which lasted until the late 1970s) had a very superficial understanding of what the word “constitutional” actually referred to compared to how the term is understood today – after several decades of debating this issue. It was, “Constitutionalism without theory”.

With the establishment of the European University Institute in Florence in 1976, the attempts by academics – interested in *understanding* the legal system of the European Communities rather than simply “making it” led to the formulation of more elaborate theories of EU constitutionalism. These efforts were greatly helped by the participation of US scholars in various projects conducted at the time, most important of which was “Integration through Law” (ITL) pursued at the EUI from 1978. While the project was led by Mauro Cappelletti, the key figure was Joseph Weiler, whose early career epitomizes “The birth of theory”, discussed in Part 3.

⁴ For an argument defending such distinction between theory and doctrine see *ibid*.

⁵ One can add the “s-word” – supranationalism, which perhaps was the true “key word” in the early debates on the nature of the European Communities. See Hugo Canihac, *La fabrique savante de l’Europe: Une archéologie des savoirs de l’Europe communautaire* (Bruylant 2020), Chapter II.

⁶ On this notion see Jan Komárek, ‘Judicial Legitimacy in the European Union’ in Claire Kilpatrick and Joanne Scott (eds), *New Legal Approaches to Studying the Court of Justice* (OUP 2020), 125-154, 131-134.

⁷ As all such periodizations, the one offered here can be contested as not giving due regard to this or that event or scholar and idea. However, I do hope that it provides a useful heuristics enabling to organize the vast material to be covered in this chapter.

The “Maastricht moment” (referring to not only the adoption of the Maastricht Treaty, but particularly the political and constitutional controversy that the Treaty gave rise to) provided impetus for the first serious *public* debate on the nature of the EU, where those critical of the “constitutional narrative” also took part. Neil MacCormick was arguably the most important scholar at that time. He formulated the idea of ‘constitutional pluralism’ in response to the Maastricht judgment of the German Federal Constitutional Court.⁸ Constitutional theory of the EU started to flourish, supported by the first-ever official process to adopt a written constitution.

The Maastricht moment also attracted communities of constitutional scholars working in their domestic contexts. Eventually, they came to understand (some very reluctantly) that it was in their interest to make inquiry into European law part of their domestic discipline. They had to accept that it would not be possible to do national constitutional law in complete ignorance of the EU and its impact on domestic constitutional settlements. This period – dating from 1992 to 2005, is discussed in Part 4 and entitled “The Maastricht moment and its aftermath”.

However, the failure of the Constitutional Treaty in 2005 and the series of crises that followed meant that the official discourse on EU constitutionalism almost evaporated, further reinforced by the painful process of adopting the Treaty of Lisbon. As is known, the Lisbon Treaty took over most of the provisions contained in the failed constitutional treaty, while it was meant to persuade the European public that the ‘constitutional concept was abandoned’.⁹ This official proclamation however did not mean that scholars stopped thinking theoretically about the EU and its law. Some of them still insist that the EU is constitutional and try to develop theories that would reflect the current state of the EU. However, important theorizations of the EU started to appear, which reject its constitutional quality. They attract more attention now, when we live in the times of “Constitutional Theory without the Constitution”, as the title of Part 5 suggests.

Before we start, a short note on the approach taken in this chapter: while there is a growing literature on legal history and sociology of European law, comparatively little has been written on the intellectual history of the discipline.¹⁰ This is even more true regarding European constitutional law or constitutional theory. While this chapter seeks to take the insights of these other disciplines into account – and in fact, it would not be possible to write it without them,¹¹ I want to show that these other disciplines miss an important part of the picture.¹² They do not capture the power of ideas – and ideologies – in the constitutional construction of European integration. It is one thing, for example, to claim that this or that actor was a “federalist”, and quite another to truly understand how constitutional lawyers – and theorists understood “federalism” *at the time* when such proclamations were being made and *why their ideas mattered*. I do not want to say that only lawyers can tell this story. However, it seems to me that

⁸ FCC, Judgment of 12 October 1993 in Cases 2 BvR 2134/92, 2 BvR 2159/92, BVerfGE 89, 155.

⁹ See Council of the European Union, Brussels, 20 July 2007, 11177/1/07, Brussels European Council of 21 and 22 June 2007, Presidency Conclusions, 15.

¹⁰ I consider Canihac, n 5, as truly pioneering and departing from more descriptive accounts by the “new legal historians”, also discussed here. Canihac admirably combines intellectual history of law and political science, as it sought to understand the nature of European Communities from their beginnings until early 1970s. In his discussion of supranationalism, however, Canihac reaches as far as into the mid-19th century.

¹¹ I mean the “new legal historians” around Morten Rasmussen, and then sociologists of law working in the bourdieusian tradition, particularly Antoine Vauchez and Antonin Cohen.

¹² This is the impression one gets from reading e.g. Antonin Cohen, ‘Constitutionalism Without Constitution: Transnational Elites Between Political Mobilization and Legal Expertise in the Making of a Constitution for Europe (1940s–1960s)’ (2007) 32 *Law & Social Inquiry* 109–135, in many ways a truly ground-breaking piece, but lacking the interest into this “internal” story I want to tell in this chapter.

only those who ‘take law seriously’¹³ can appreciate such nuances and render them intelligible: to lawyers, but hopefully to others as well. This chapter shall serve as invitation to such inquiry.¹⁴

2. Constitutionalism without theory, 1952-1978

While ‘constitutionalism’ has been part and parcel of the early debates on the legal order of the European Communities, two other notions were more prominent: federalism and particularly supranationalism.¹⁵ Federalism reflected political ambitions of those who wanted to prevent the misuse of power by the nation state and to unite the peoples of Europe into a “true federation”. As such the word “federalism” has probably been the most visible in public contestations of European integration.¹⁶ Supranationalism was a more technical term intended to separate the legal order of the early European Communities from its international origins, something that has remained contested until today among lawyers (while the general public probably does not even know about the controversy).¹⁷ In the early years (1950s and 1960s), the real ‘semantic struggle’¹⁸ has been about these two terms, while the constitutional – as opposed to international – nature of the legal order of the Communities concerned a narrower issue: legal authority, especially that of the ECSC’s High Authority and later the Court of Justice and its rulings.

The first international academic congress on the ECSC, which took place in Milan-Stresa in 1957, was the high point in this early debate.¹⁹ As legal historians documented, the Congress was disappointing for those with supranational ambitions, since the consensus emerging from the conference was that the ECSC was a conventional international organisation.²⁰ This conclusion reached by the most important committee of the Congress composed mostly of international law professors, was however quickly attacked by a diverse group of “dissenters”. They had formed a relatively cohesive group, which later gave rise to a new discipline: Community law. At the same time, the political nature of the whole “scholarly” enterprise was

¹³ Here I do not want to invoke Ronald Dworkin, but Christian Joerges, ‘Taking the Law Seriously: On Political Science and the Role of Law in the Process of European Integration’ (1996) 2 *European Law Journal* 105-135.

¹⁴ Jan Komárek: ‘Whose ideas matter? Studying the origins of European constitutional imaginaries’ *IMAGINE Working Paper* No. 21, *iCourts Working Paper Series* No. 300, available at https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=4220889 (accessed 26 January 2023) seeks to map the field.

¹⁵ See Canihac, n 5.

¹⁶ On federalism in the context of European integration see Michael Burgess, *Federalism and European Union: The Building of Europe, 1950-2000* (Routledge 2000).

¹⁷ In this relation, the contribution by Jiří Malenovský, judge at the Court of Justice of the EU between 2004-2021, is remarkable: ‘A la recherche d’une solution intersystémique aux rapports du droit international et du droit de l’union européenne’ (2019) 65 *Annuaire Français de Droit International* 201-234. Malenovský argues that EU law ‘constitutes a highly autonomous subsystem of international law’. See also Bruno de Witte, ‘The EU as an international legal experiment’ in Joseph HH Weiler and Gráinne de Búrca, *The Worlds of European Constitutionalism* (CUP 2011), 19-56.

¹⁸ See n 6 on this notion.

¹⁹ On this congress see Julie Bailleux and Simon Jackson, “‘How Europe became law’ The first international academic congress on the ECSC (Milan-Stresa 1957)’ (2010) 60 *Revue française de science politique (English)* 67-90 and Canihac, n 5, 125-130.

²⁰ See Bailleux/Jackson, n 19, 83.

immediately observed by some internationalists, showing that the stakes in these scholarly debates concerned the very nature and legitimate boundaries of legal scholarship as such.²¹

This chapter deals with ideas and theories and not so much personal biographies or institutional histories that lay at the centre of historians and sociologists' work. Their work allows us, however, to choose the key figures, whose ideas are important to focus on. We shall see that these were not legal scholars (let alone theorists) working at universities of the time, but rather lawyers-diplomats, who firstly negotiated the treaties as members of national delegations. They later took up some key positions in the institutions of the new Communities and continued in their efforts to make the Communities constitutional.²²

Two figures stand out among them: Walter Hallstein and Pierre Pescatore,²³ as they illustrate some of the key features of the debate concerning the legal nature of the Communities: the relative shallowness of constitutional claims made by various protagonists; the importance of the US federal experience when such claims were being formulated; and finally, something that cannot be elaborated here fully, that their propositions were far from being accepted in their own professional communities – and yet, today, they are the ones remembered and still referred to, contrary to their opponents of the time, who need to be uncovered by legal historians.²⁴

(a) Hallstein's "Europe in the making"

Walter Hallstein, the first President of the EEC's Commission needs to be addressed first.²⁵ His intellectual background and career before he became the key figure in the debate on the nature of the early Communities and their legal system sheds some light on the intellectual origins of his thinking about Europe.²⁶

²¹ See particularly Canihac, n 5, 141-143 and also Bailleux/Jackson, n 19, 85. In this respect one must note the role of the *Fédération internationale pour le droit européen* (FIDE). Its true purpose seems to have been to provide particular answers to legal problems of the time with scholarly authority rather than to seek a "mere" understanding" of European law. On FIDE see Rebekka Byberg, 'A Miscellaneous Network: The History of FIDE 1961-94' (2017) 57 *American Journal of Legal History* 142-165 with references to earlier works, particularly by Karen Alter, who has been a true pioneer in this respect.

²² See Morten Rasmussen, 'Agents of Constitutionalism: The Quest for a Constitutional Breakthrough in European Law, 1945- 1964' in Marcus M. Payk and Kim Christian Priemel (eds), *Crafting the International Order* (OUP 2021), 249-275 with further references, and Anne Boerger and Morten Rasmussen, 'Transforming European Law: The Establishment of the Constitutional Discourse from 1950 to 1993' (2014) 10 *European Constitutional Law Review* 199-225.

²³ Rasmussen, n 22, includes among the 'agents of constitutionalism' also 'the Dutch trade unionist, politician, federalist, and failed legal student, Petrus Serrarens' (250, and in detail 259-263), 'director of the legal service, French lawyer and civil servant Michel Gaudet (250 and in detail 263-268), 'the French politician and lawyer, Robert Lecourt, and the Italian law professor, Alberto Trabucchi' (250-251 and in detail 269-273). In this chapter we are however mostly concerned with ideas and theories, not the agents or actors.

²⁴ See especially Bill Davies, 'Resistance to European Law and Constitutional Identity in Germany: Herbert Kraus and Solange in its Intellectual Context' (2015) 21 *European Law Journal* 434-459.

²⁵ Served two terms between 1958 and 1967, when he resigned in response to the 'Empty chair crisis' and the pressure from the French president Charles De Gaulle. On Hallstein's life and role in European integration see Rasmussen, n 22, 251-258 and Wilfried Loth, William Wallace and Wolfgang Wessels (eds), *Walter Hallstein: The Forgotten European?* (Macmillan 1998).

²⁶ See Hugo Canihac, 'The Making of an Imagined 'Community of Law': Law, Market and Democracy in the Early Constitutional Imaginaries of European Integration' (2022) 18 *European Constitutional Law Review* 2-29.

Hallstein was appointed a professor in 1930 in fields that had little to do with public or constitutional law.²⁷ He had been drafted into *Wehrmacht* in 1942 and captured by the allied forces in 1944. The rest of the war Hallstein spent in a prisoner of war camp in the United States to return to Germany where he ‘gradually became part of the new political elite in the American zone of occupation that would come to dominate the institutions of the Federal Republic of Germany’.²⁸ The American influence on Hallstein was reinforced by his study visit to the Georgetown University in 1948. Few years later, in his lecture at the same university in 1952, when recounting the negotiations on the Schuman Plan, Hallstein stated that ‘the Schuman-Plan in its constitutional structure intentionally anticipates the institutions of the future all-in Federation of Europe’.²⁹

The most complete statement of his vision of Europe can be found in English in *Europe in the Making* published in 1973.³⁰ While the book provides some “theoretical perspectives” on European integration, it can hardly be seen as a true “constitutional theory”. The key chapter of the book is entitled ‘Law in Place of Force’, which exemplifies the trust which Hallstein put into ‘integration through law’ long before the term was appropriated by the academic project conducted in Florence few years later.

Hallstein spends some lines on the notion of “Community”,³¹ which to him is the best conceptualisation of the entity that is neither federal or confederal ‘in the contrasting terminology of nineteenth-century constitutional theory’.³² He also makes clear that the Community is neither international nor unitary, but supranational – relating to the debates at the very origins of European integration.³³

Regarding the constitution, Hallstein is remarkably undemanding: ‘The Community, like every association – be it of individuals or private or public bodies – has a constitution’.³⁴ One is immediately reminded of the quip made decades later in the (finally) political contestation over the Treaty Establishing a Constitution of Europe by the British foreign minister: ‘Golf Clubs too have constitutions’.³⁵ The foundations of what later became characterized as

²⁷ He was firstly appointed as the Chair of Private and Company Law at the University of Rostock in 1930 and then took the Chair of Commercial and Labour Law, Comparative Law and International Private Law at the University of Frankfurt am Main in 1941.

²⁸ Rasmussen, n 22, 252.

²⁹ Walter Hallstein, ‘The Schuman-Plan and the Integration of Europe’, Lecture at Georgetown University, 12 March 1952, cited from Anne Boerger, ‘Negotiating the Foundations of European Law 1950–1957’, (2012) 21 *Contemporary European History* 339–56, 342, fn. 12.

³⁰ Translated by Charles Rotter, Norton 1973. It is the translation of *Der unvollendete Bundesstaat: Europäische Erfahrungen und Erkenntnisse* (Econ Verlag 1969). It largely corresponds to another Hallstein’s book, *Die Europäische Gemeinschaft* (Econ Verlag 1973), published in several editions since this first.

³¹ Hallstein, n 30, 37-41.

³² *Ibid*, 40. Interestingly, in his earlier book, *United Europe: Challenge and Opportunity* (HUP 1962), which was the published version of his William L. Clayton Lectures on International Economic Affairs and Foreign Policy, given at The Fletcher School of Law and Diplomacy, Tufts University in April 1972, Hallstein notes at 29 that ‘Just as language precedes grammar, so politics precedes political theory; and disputes as to the proper terminology for what we are doing in the European Community sometimes seem to me as academic as grammarians’ controversies’. It seems that few years later the power of the word has been realised by Hallstein...

³³ As the book is more an argument than analysis, Hallstein is however cautious regarding this term: ‘because the use of the word “supranational” appears to some to imply that we are bent upon destroying national identities’. Federalism is excluded on similarly pragmatic grounds.

³⁴ Hallstein, n 30, 40.

³⁵ Matthias Kumm, ‘Beyond Golf Clubs and the Judicialization of Politics: Why Europe has a Constitution Properly So Called’ (2006) 54 *American Journal of Comparative Law* Issue suppl.1, 505–530, 530.

constitutionalizing jurisprudence of the Court of Justice³⁶ are mentioned in a different part of the chapter, where Hallstein characterizes Community law ‘as a legal system’.³⁷ It is quite likely that at that time, whether or not the Community had a constitution was not seen important or even worthy some lengthy discussion.

The point is not to dismiss Hallstein’s book as “bad” or too unsophisticated theory, as it was not written as such. Rather, the book was an equivalent to *The Federalist Papers*, which were ‘calculated to build support for [the new Constitution] ratification’ in the State of New York, since ‘[f]ew believed that defeat in such a major state would be survivable’.³⁸ *Europe in the Making* wanted to *make* Europe constitutional rather than merely *understand* it.

Constitutionalism for Hallstein meant primarily legal authority, centred around the Court of Justice: ‘In setting up a European Court of Justice, our aim was very ambitious: to crown the constitutional structure of the Community with a Supreme Court which was a truly constitutional body’.³⁹ This is what Hallstein’s approach shares with Pierre Pescatore, another important figure of the early period.

(b) Pescatore’s “law of integration”

Pescatore came to the ‘law of integration’ – the concept he coined in his book published in 1973,⁴⁰ later than the lawyers who participated in the Stresa debates.⁴¹ His professional career started in the Luxembourgish diplomatic service right after his graduation at the University of Louvain in 1946. Pescatore was appointed secretary of Luxembourg’s delegation at the second session of the United Nations’ first General Assembly, where, similarly to his contemporary Eric Stein he became disenchanted with international affairs governed by politics rather than rules. His first engagement with Community affairs was in the *Group de rédaction* in 1956 composed of lawyers who were preparing the final wording of the Treaty of Rome.⁴²

Throughout his all life, and alongside his other professional positions in the Luxembourgish diplomatic service and later at the Court of Justice (1967 and 1985), Pescatore was a prolific author of academic publications.⁴³ However, when taking a closer look at these, we can also see the lack of some deeper engagement with theoretical issues. Similarly to Hallstein,

³⁶ See e.g. Oliver Gerstenberg, *Euroconstitutionalism and its Discontents* (OUP 2018).

³⁷ Hallstein, n 30, 33: ‘What the member states have done by founding the Community is to surrender a part of their separate national sovereignty, and to create an entirely new and independent legal system to which both they as states and their citizens are subject’.

³⁸ Ian Shapiro, ‘Introduction. The Federalist *Then and Now*’ in Ibid (ed), *The Federalist papers: Alexander Hamilton, James Madison, John Jay* (Yale UP 2009), ix-xxii, x.

³⁹ Hallstein, n 30, 34.

⁴⁰ *Le droit de l’intégration. Emergence d’un phénomène nouveau dans les relations internationales selon l’expérience des Communautés Européennes* (Sijthoff, 1972), in English published as *The law of integration: emergence of a new phenomenon in international relations, based on the experience of the European Communities* (Sijthoff 1974).

⁴¹ On Pescatore see Vera Fritz, ‘Activism on and off the Bench: Pierre Pescatore and the Law of Integration’ (2020) 57 *Common Market Law Review* 475-502. I drew on this article regarding Pescatore’s life and career.

⁴² Fritz, n 41, 481. On the ‘group’ see Anne Boerger-De Smedt, ‘Negotiating the foundations of European Law, 1950–1957, The legal history of the Treaties of Paris and Rome’ (2012) 21 *Contemporary European History* 339-356.

⁴³ Apart from *The Law of Integration* (n 40) see the collection of his most important writings published as Pierre Pescatore, *Etudes de droit communautaire européen. 1962-2007* (Bruylant 2008).

Pescatore e.g. notes in his article on ‘The Court of Justice as the Federal and Constitutional Court’ that

[t]he concept of the constitution is known to us mainly from public law, but in reality it is a general concept of law. We find it from private law (“statutes” of the civil, commercial, economic and syndicalist formations of various types), over public law, where the notion is particularly developed (constitution of states, unitary or federal), towards international law (constitution of international organizations and the global constitution of the “community of international law”).⁴⁴

Pescatore notes the fundamental character of constitutions as they ‘establish a human society and provide the basis for the legal order of that society, from which follows the essential, “existential” character of any constitutional law’.⁴⁵ But all he says on account of the Community legal order is that the Treaties created a new social structure (among the six member states), thereby corresponding to the constitutional characteristics outlined above. Federalism refers mostly to the system of divided powers between the Community and the member states, while the federal and constitutional role of the Court consist mainly in the policing the boundaries between them and safeguarding the hierarchy of legal norms in the system.

Pescatore’s audience was different than Hallstein’s, as he did not address the general public, but was writing for other lawyers – in practice and academia. However, if the aim to understand rather than to advocate for a particular solution is what differentiates theory from other legal scholarship, then it is hard to see Pescatore’s oeuvre as the former. It is sophisticated scholarly analysis, something indistinguishable from legal advocacy.

(c) Constitutional theories – and imaginaries

It would certainly be interesting to try to reconstruct the implicit (or underlying) theories on which Hallstein’s, Pescatore’s (and many others’) writings in this early period were based. For the sake of space we need to move on to the next part of our story. Before we do so, however, let us briefly reflect on the difference between these early understandings of constitutionalism on the one hand, and how this concept has been conceived more recently.

To understand the difference, the concept of constitutional imaginary will be helpful: it refers to sets of ideas and beliefs that help to motivate and justify the practice of government and collective self-rule. Such imaginaries are as important as institutions and office-holders, since they provide political action with an overarching sense and purpose recognized by those governed as legitimate. Constitutional lawyers – especially, but not only, scholars are important co-producers of such imaginaries, which however need to have grounding outside the community of legal experts.⁴⁶ Constitutional imaginaries of European states changed radically throughout the process of European integration – not only in terms of their increasing embedding in the international system (culminating in what we call “globalisation”), but also

⁴⁴ ‘La Cour en tant que juridiction fédérale et constitutionnelle’ [1965], reprinted in Pescatore, n 43, 61-96, 64.

⁴⁵ Ibid.

⁴⁶ On the concept see Jan Komárek, ‘European Constitutional Imaginaries: Utopias, Ideologies and the Other’ in Jan Komárek (ed), *European Constitutional Imaginaries. Between Ideology and Utopia* (OUP 2023), 1-17, 2.

regarding the place of constitutions, legal institutions (especially courts) and the language they use (rights).⁴⁷

In the early post-war period, constitutions did not occupy such central place in public life. Gradually, however, Western societies were turning away from the state and other collective institutions and arrangements as the guarantors of good life towards markets and individualism.⁴⁸ Constitutions have been gradually ‘elevated from [their] original task of regulating relations between governmental institutions to the symbolic representation of social unity’.⁴⁹ In other words, constitutions in the early post-war period were not invested with the task of holding societies together.⁵⁰ The prominence of “constitutional identity” in our current debates or the emergence of a theory of “constitutional patriotism” represent this change.

Seen in this light, lots of other writings from the early period fall short of what we today would understand as *constitutional* theories. That is why Hans Peter Ipsen’s idea of European Communities as ‘purposive associations of functional integration’, will not be discussed here, although it may have capture the issue in much more realistic terms. Ipsen explicitly notes in the introduction to his lecture on the constitutional perspectives of the European Communities, that he will do so without arguing ‘from analogies and comparisons that were familiar to [him] under constitutional law’.⁵¹ His focus on the economic dimension of European integration, stripped of its political dimension, was even farther from constitutional theory than Hallstein or Pescatore.

3. The birth of theory, 1978-1992

(a) *European University Institute: more than a “think tank” for the Community*

While the establishment of the *Common Market Law Review* in 1963 and FIDE in 1961 certainly helped to start transnational reflections on the nature of the integration project *among academics* outside the rather small circle of Community insiders, contributions to this debate had remained rather under-theorized. According to the historian Rebekka Byberg, most articles published in *Common Market Law Review* between 1963 and 1974 were ‘doctrinal pieces attempting to clarify the latest ECJ rulings without explicit theoretical or contextual considerations’.⁵² In the later period (1974-1983) the articles sought to defend the authority of the Court of Justice against the raising scepticism by some national courts.⁵³ This was also due to the close ties between the Review and Community institutions, especially the Legal Service

⁴⁷ See on this development Martin Loughlin, *Against Constitutionalism* (HUP 2022). Regarding Germany, Michaela Haibronner, *Traditions and Transformations. The Rise of German Constitutionalism* (OUP 2015) is instructive.

⁴⁸ This is usually referred to as the rise of neoliberalism that started in the 1970s. See Daniel T. Rodgers, *Age of Fracture* (Belknap Press 2011) for the United States.

⁴⁹ Loughlin, 47, 191.

⁵⁰ On this point, regarding Germany, see Justin Collings, ‘The elites, the people, and their court’ in Marco Dani, Marco Goldoni, and Agustín J. Menéndez (eds), *The Legitimacy of European Constitutional Orders: A Comparative Inquiry* (Edward Elgar 2023), 214-233.

⁵¹ Hans Peter Ipsen, *Verfassungsperspektiven der Europäischen Gemeinschaften: Vortrag gehalten vor der Berliner Juristischen Gesellschaft am 17. April 1970* (De Gruyter 1970), 1. On Ipsen and his writings on European integration see (critically, connecting them to Ipsen’s Nazi past), Christian Joerges, ‘Europe a *Großraum*? Shifting Legal Conceptualizations of the Integration Project’ in *Ibid*, *Conflict and Transformation: Essays on European Law and Policy* (Hart 2022) 546-558, 548-551.

⁵² Rebekka Byberg, ‘The History of Common Market Law Review 1963-1993: Carving out an Academic Space for Europe’ (2017) 23 *European Law Journal* 45-65, 54.

⁵³ *Ibid*, 57-59.

of the Commission,⁵⁴ and to some extent also the Court of Justice.⁵⁵ The confession made by one of the prominent academic figures of the time, Henry Schermers, illustrates this rather well. Writing in 1990, he said:

When the Community was young and vulnerable and not yet generally accepted we fought for the powers of the Court of Justice. Uniformity of Community law, even the creation of Community law as a legal system required unrestricted authority of the Community Court. But has the situation not changed? Now that the Court of Justice has authority and a substantial amount of power, are there no reasons which may justify some control over it?⁵⁶

The key moment came with the establishment of the European University Institute in 1976 and especially the “Integration through Law” project (‘ITL project’), which started in 1978.⁵⁷ Mauro Cappelletti, one of the first-generation professors of the EUI’s Department of Law, put together the most ambitious academic endeavour concerning Community law so far, aiming to ‘examine the role of law in the process of European integration as seen against the American federal experience’.⁵⁸ It gathered tens of scholars (and practitioners) from both sides of the Atlantic, who produced a multi-volume publication ranging from more theoretical issues included in a three-book volume I on *Methods, Tools and Institutions*, and five other volumes examining various fields of substantive law. Besides these publications, the project provided ‘a superstructure for seminars and research student activities’ and helped scholars who participated in the project and had previously had no links to Community’s legal and political practice to get connected – so that some called the EUI ‘an EU think tank’.⁵⁹

It was the participation of US scholars and the interdisciplinary nature of the ITL project which gave rise to the birth of first theory of Community law.⁶⁰ The following, certainly over-quoted, passage illustrates why. Commenting on a contribution by Ami Barav, ‘then one of Europe’s leading scholars of European Community law’,⁶¹ the American political scientist Martin Shapiro said that such writing

represents a stage of constitutional scholarship out of which American constitutional law must have passed about seventy years ago (although remnants of it are still to be found). It is constitutional law without politics. Professor Barav

⁵⁴ Byberg, n 52, 56-57 mentions e.g. Claus-Dieter Ehlermann, the director of the Legal Service of the Commission.

⁵⁵ Especially David O’Keeffe, the legal secretary to the ECJ judge O’Higgins – see Byberg, n 52, 59.

⁵⁶ Henry G. Schermers, ‘The Scales in Balance: National Constitutional Court v. Court of Justice’, (1990) 27 *Common Market Law Review* 97–105, at 103 quoted in Byberg, n 52, 63.

⁵⁷ Rebekka Byberg, ‘The History of the Integration Through Law Project: Creating the Academic Expression of a Constitutional Legal Vision for Europe’ (2017) 18 *German Law Journal* 1531-1556.

⁵⁸ Mauro Cappelletti, Monica Seccombe and Joseph Weiler, ‘Integration Through Law: Europe and the American Federal Experience. A General Introduction’ in Mauro Cappelletti, Monica Seccombe and Joseph Weiler (eds), *Integration Through Law: Europe and the American Federal Experience. Volume 1: Methods, Tools and Institutions. Book 1: A Political, Legal and Economic Overview*, 3-68, 3.

⁵⁹ See e.g. Byberg, n 57, 1532.

⁶⁰ One may add one more dimension where the United States played the key role: money. The Ford Foundation supported the Integration through Law project, but also numerous other activities that preceded it. On this see Antonin Cohen, ‘La structuration atlantique des European Studies: La Fondation Ford et l’institut de la Communauté européenne pour les études universitaires dans la génération d’un “objet”’ (2017) 67 *Revue française de science politique* 69-96.

⁶¹ Anthony Arnall, ‘The Americanization of EU law Scholarship’ in Anthony Arnall, Piet Eeckhout, and Takis Tridimas (eds), *Continuity and Change in EU Law: Essays in Honour of Sir Francis Jacobs* (OUP 2008), 415-431, 424.

presents the Community as a juristic idea; the written constitution as a sacred text; the professional commentary as a legal truth; the case law as the inevitable working out of the correct implications of the constitutional text; and the constitutional court as the disembodied voice of right reason and constitutional teleology.⁶²

Shapiro was right: Barav had been writing in the tradition of legal scholarship which was a-theoretical, as it aimed to *construe* Community law (*as distinctive from international law*) and support it with scholarly authority rather than critically analyse it. In defence of Barav, one may observe that Shapiro (as a political scientist) possibly did not appreciate the importance of doctrinal legal scholarship for any legal system, including that of the United States.⁶³ What he characterized as ‘remnants’ were probably such doctrinal pieces, aimed at legal practice rather than other scholars. However, in the 1980s Critical Legal Studies movement was on the rise in the United States, bringing legal scholars farther from internal perspectives on law towards detached critiques from the outside, using all sorts of other disciplines – including political science. Their participation in the ITL project certainly encouraged similarly critical approaches by the new generation of legal scholars who were not so invested in building Europe.

This was closely tied to interdisciplinarity, which to Cappelletti appeared ‘almost as an exercise in intellectual federalism, [as] all through the project there was an effort of coordination aimed at making of an inherently and proudly pluralistic product, a coherent research effort united in its most basic vision and rationales’.⁶⁴ This then became the approach followed by scholars at the EUI, making it an avant-garde place for studying Europe (and law), and not merely an ‘EU think tank’.

(b) Joseph Weiler: connecting legal and political analysis into one frame

Shapiro played an important role in the ITL project as the coordinator of contributions by the US scholars and his critique was taken to heart by someone who in my view gave rise to the first true theory of legal integration: Joseph Weiler. His PhD thesis written under Cappelletti’s supervision is introduced thus: ‘The primary goal of my own study will be precisely to meet this critique of, and challenge to, European legal literature’.⁶⁵ And so it did.⁶⁶

Weiler joined the project as Cappelletti’s research assistant after graduating from the LL.M. programme of the Faculty of Law at the University of Cambridge.⁶⁷ As the early

⁶² Martin Shapiro, ‘Comparative Law and Politics’ (1980) 53 *Southern California Law Review* 537-542, 538.

⁶³ John Reitz, ‘The Importance of and Need for Legal Science’ (2013) 21 *Transnational Law & Contemporary Problems* 647-666; Pierre Schlag and Amy J. Griffin, *How to Do Things with Legal Doctrine* (University of Chicago Press 2020).

⁶⁴ Mauro Cappelletti, ‘Foreword to the Florence Integration Project Series’, in Cappelletti, Seccombe, Weiler, n 58, v-ix, v.

⁶⁵ *Supranational law and the supranational system: Legal structure and political process in the European Community*, 1-2. The thesis is available here: <http://hdl.handle.net/1814/4822>. It was preceded by two publications: ‘Supranationalism Revisited: Retrospective and Prospective. The European Communities After Thirty Years’, *EUI Working Paper* No. 2, available at <http://hdl.handle.net/1814/23228> and Joseph Weiler, ‘The Community System: the Dual Character of Supranationalism’ (1984) 1 *Yearbook of European Law* 267-306.

⁶⁶ The following three paragraphs are based on Jan Komárek, ‘Why Read The Transformation of Europe Today? On the Limits of a Liberal Constitutional Imaginary’ in Jan Komárek (ed), *European Constitutional Imaginaries: Between Ideology and Utopia* (OUP 2023), 119-146, 123-124.

⁶⁷ On the history of this project and Joseph Weiler’s role in it see Rebekka Byberg, ‘The History of the Integration Through Law Project: Creating the Academic Expression of a Constitutional Legal Vision for Europe’ (2017) 18 *German Law Journal* 1531-1556. I would like to express my deepest gratitude to Rebekka and her PhD thesis

correspondence between Cappelletti and Weiler shows, the latter's interest in European integration was initially motivated by his concern with the Israel-Palestinian conflict.⁶⁸ As he wrote some years later in an article that resulted from this original interest, '[p]articularly inspiring [was] the rehabilitation, of which the European Communities Common Market [was] a major facet, that brought former enemies together in a regional joint venture'.⁶⁹ This, in my view contributed to Weiler's detached analysis of the dynamics between law and politics in European integration, something that marked his theoretical approach.

Another important element in Weiler's revolutionary approach to the study of Community law is a piece written as a reaction to political scientists' and international relations scholars' scepticism towards supranationalism and the prospects of European integration in general. Such scepticism was widespread at the time when Weiler worked on his doctoral dissertation.⁷⁰ The conference of "Europeanists" in Washington, DC in October 1980 was perhaps the moment when Weiler realized the gap in the understanding of European integration between lawyers like him and the other two disciplines. He therefore started to "teach" the latter about the importance of law.⁷¹

The piece and the whole encounter of Joseph Weiler with the other two disciplines was crucial for the later scholarly influence of Weiler's approach. It is because what Weiler described as 'the "constitutionalisation" of the Community legal structure' in 'The Transformation of Europe' – a piece that is truly foundational for European constitutional theory, was taken at that time (in the early 1990s) by a new generation of political science and international relations scholars (Anne Marie Slaughter, Andrew Moravcsik, Karen Alter and others) in the United States as something that *correctly describes* the state of law (which they, as outsiders to the discipline, could not independently assess, only accept).⁷² The article, published in 1991 by Yale Law Journal had built on Weiler's PhD thesis and developed it into a more philosophical reflection of the place of law and politics in European integration.

Adding politics into the analysis (instead of seeing law and politics as two separate spheres, which need to be understood through different tools) was perhaps what made Weiler's contribution so profound. It was an "integrative theory" not in the sense of promoting integration, but in that it was capable to find conceptual apparatus through which constitutional law and politics could be seen as two distinct, but at the same connected and mutually

supervisor Morten Rasmussen for sharing with me the archive of Mauro Cappelletti, held by the *Historical Archives of the European Union*.

⁶⁸ The original title of his dissertation was thus 'The Potential Application of Supranational Principles in the Middle East' and was co-supervised by two Israeli scholars, Nathan Feinberg, then Professor Emeritus at the Hebrew University, and Professor David Vital of the Tel-Aviv University. See letter from Nathan Feinberg to Terence Daintith, 16 May 1982 and letter from Joseph Weiler to Mauro Cappelletti, 27 October 1980, both on file with the *Historical Archives of the European Union*, Mauro Cappelletti).

⁶⁹ See Joseph H. Weiler, 'Israel and the Creation of a Palestinian State: The Art of the Impossible and the Possible' (1982) 17 *Texas International Law Journal* 287-385, 330.

⁷⁰ Joseph Weiler, 'Community, Member States and European Integration: Is the Law Relevant?' (1982) 21 *Journal of Common Market Studies* 39-56. See also Weiler's observations in Weiler, n 69, 331-333.

⁷¹ The piece referred to in n 70 begins (at 39), without reference, with a direct quotation from Stanley Hofmann, 'Reflections on the Nation-State in Western Europe Today' (1982) 21 *Journal of Common Market Studies* 21-37 – 'as Stanley Hofmann aptly suggest, "[t]oday's reality is complex and messy'. In one of the lectures in the Total Law course of 2006 Weiler referred to this conference as the moment when he realized the gap.

⁷² I owe this point to Karen Alter. See particularly Anne-Marie Slaughter, Andrew S. Tulumello and Stepan Wood, 'International Law and International Relations Theory: A New Generation of Interdisciplinary Scholarship' (1998) 92 *American Journal of International Law* 367-397.

conditioning each other. There is no politics without law as much there is no law without politics, although it can take considerable effort to make the latter visible in the legal analysis.

4. The Maastricht moment and its aftermath, 1992-2005

(a) The Maastricht moment

Alongside the EUI and the ITL project discussed above, it was the “rebellion” by the German Federal Constitutional Court (the FCC)⁷³ that gave birth to the constitutional theory of European law. Constitutional pluralism was possibly the very first constitutional theory that sought to conceptualize the EU legal order in completely new terms, challenging some key assumptions of the state-based constitutional theory in response to this ruling.

The key debate of that time took place in the *European Law Journal*, established at the EUI as a counterpart to the *Common Market Law Review*.⁷⁴ The journal’s ambition was to provide a scholarly platform where, in contrast to ‘traditional scholarship’, law would be studied “in context”.⁷⁵ Two features of the debate published in the journal in 1995 were particularly important:

First, the key protagonists, Neil MacCormick and Jürgen Habermas, were not Community law scholars, but (legal) philosophers (if one can put a single label on such great minds who contributed so widely to European thought). At the time MacCormick worked on the conceptualisation of law ‘Beyond the Sovereign State’ – the title of the twenty-first Chorley Lecture, delivered at the London School of Economics on 3 June 1992.⁷⁶ His article, ‘The Maastricht-Urteil: Sovereignty Now’,⁷⁷ became foundational for a possibly first-ever theory of law that did justice to the unique nature of the EU: constitutional pluralism.⁷⁸ It was a genuine attempt to re-think the foundations of constitutional thought in Europe, that had their roots in the work of Hans Kelsen and Carl Schmitt. MacCormick’s *Questioning Sovereignty* published in 1999⁷⁹ was then the culmination of this work, which inspired numerous legal and constitutional theorists to engage with European law and the Union. Neil Walker was probably the most important of them.

Habermas’s contribution⁸⁰ was only a short reply to Dieter Grimm’s article ‘Does Europe Need a Constitution?’,⁸¹ but built on the work that was just published in Germany and became his

⁷³ See n 8. On the political and social context of the whole post-Maastricht era see Michael A. Wilkinson, ‘Political constitutionalism in Europe revisited’ (2023) 50 *Journal of Law and Society, Supplement: Political Constitutions in Transnational Society: Socio-Legal and Interdisciplinary Perspectives* S115-S139.

⁷⁴ Interview with Joseph Weiler conducted by Jan Komárek and Päivi Leino-Sanberg at NYU School of Law, 17 May 2023.

⁷⁵ Francis Snyder, Editorial (1995) 1 *European Law Journal* 1-4, 3.

⁷⁶ (1993) 56 *Modern Law Review* 1-18.

⁷⁷ (1995) 1 *European Law Journal* 259-266.

⁷⁸ See Matej Avbelj and Jan Komárek (eds), *Constitutional Pluralism in Europe and Beyond* (Hart 2012).

⁷⁹ *Questioning Sovereignty: Law, State, and Nation in the European Commonwealth* (OUP 1999).

⁸⁰ ‘Remarks on Dieter Grimm’s ‘Does Europe Need a Constitution?’ (1995) 1 *European Law Journal* 303-307.

⁸¹ (1995) 1 *European Law Journal* 282-302.

most significant contribution to the theory of law and democracy – *Between Facts and Norms*.⁸² Habermas was an important contributor to the debate on the very possibility of European constitution and his theory of law and democracy then inspired numerous legal scholars in Germany and elsewhere, most importantly Armin von Bogdandy.⁸³

Both MacCormick and Habermas intended to re-think some central categories of constitutional thought: sovereignty, legal (and institutional) hierarchy, nation- and state- hood, democratic legitimacy, or citizenship, taking into account the transformations of the state in the era of ever intensifying international cooperation (and rising interdependence). Such ideas coincided with analogous attempts to re-think international law and order – that were increasingly being perceived as “post-sovereign”, “post-Westphalian” and in the need of establishing their legitimacy on different grounds.⁸⁴

Dieter Grimm’s contribution in the ELJ debate signifies its second important feature. The “Maastricht moment” forced German professoriate to participate in the international (or to be precise, European) debate on the EU’s constitution.⁸⁵ As Grimm recalls those times in a book interview: ‘For me, and for others as well, *Maastricht* was the turning point. Maastricht made clear for the first time that constitutional law could no longer be treated without European law (and that the same was true, incidentally, of international law)’.⁸⁶ Dieter Grimm, judge at the FCC which delivered the Maastricht decision, had to be taken seriously also at the European plane – not only because he was German, but also as he was very well integrated into the emerging transnational intellectual elite and became, among many other things, a regular participant to the Global Constitutionalism Seminar established in 1996 at Yale Law School.⁸⁷

The Maastricht moment was therefore a wake-up call to German constitutional scholars, who realised that in order to further influence the debate that had direct consequences in their country as well, they had to communicate in English. As aptly expressed by Armin von Bogdandy, then a member of the younger generation of public law scholars in Germany:

German, Italian, Spanish and French scholars and, indeed, lawyers in general, if they wish to participate in the Europeanisation of European law, find themselves in a similar position vis-à-vis this Anglo-American dominance as the French, Italian and Belgian currencies did vis-à-vis the German monetary policy before 1999. The way to participation is largely set by the strongest system’s rules. In monetary terms, this meant accepting Germany’s monetary and fiscal philosophy; in terms of

⁸² First published in Germany as *Faktizität und Geltung: Beiträge zur Diskurstheorie des Rechts und des demokratischen Rechtsstaats* (Suhrkamp 1992). On the importance of this work for European constitutionalism see John P. McCormick, ‘Habermas, Supranational Democracy and the European Constitution’ (2006) 2 *European Constitutional Law Review* 398–423.

⁸³ See particularly Armin von Bogdandy, ‘The European Lesson for International Democracy: The Significance of Articles 9–12 EU Treaty for International Organizations’ (2012) 23 *European Journal of International Law* 315–334.

⁸⁴ See Jan Klabbers, Anne Peters, Geir Ulfstein, *The Constitutionalization of International Law* (OUP 2009). For an influential critique see Martti Koskeniemi, ‘Constitutionalism as Mindset: Reflections on Kantian Themes About International Law and Globalization’ (2007) 8 *Theoretical Inquiries in Law* 9–36.

⁸⁵ On this point see

⁸⁶ Dieter Grimm in conversation with Oliver Lepsius, Christian Waldhoff and Matthias Rossbach, *Advocate of the Constitution* (OUP 2020), 111, reference omitted.

⁸⁷ Grimm et al, n 86, 161.

the Europeanisation of European law, it means using the English language, the Anglo-American legal categories and probably also their argumentation culture.⁸⁸

The following subsection seeks to provide a brief overview of the most significant strands in EU constitutional theory between Maastricht (1993) and the failure of the Treaty Establishing a Constitution for Europe⁸⁹ – an attempt to adopt a written constitution at the time of the EU’s most significant enlargement. The rejection by the Dutch and much more importantly French electorate in 2005⁹⁰ signified the ascent of a new era: that of theorizing about the EU constitution at times when political and constitutional practice reject its existence.

(b) EU constitutional theory in times of liberal hegemony

The Maastricht moment – albeit threatening from the perspective of lawyers-advocates and politicians, was therefore a blessing for constitutional theory, as it opened doors to theorizing the EU and its legal order “beyond the state”. It happened in a unique period of 1990s, when liberal ideology and “new constitutionalism” dominated the “new world order”.⁹¹ The attempt to provide the EU with a “true” (that is written) constitution came at the end of this era, which culminated before the terrorist attacks in the United States on 11 September 2001. The world was to become less liberal and more openly violent again.

Constitutional theories of the EU flourished. The following cannot provide a complete overview of all of them, and the focus on those published in English partly reflects Von Bogdandy’s observation cited above, and partly results from the present author’s linguistic limitations. However, it hopefully maps the key strands of EU constitutional theory of that time, which in fact continue to influence the teaching and thinking of Europe and its legal order until today. As will be seen, many of them originated at the Law Department of the EUI, which had become the intellectual centre of constitutional debates in Europe.

Firstly, there continued to be an interest in ‘comparative federalism’, where Daniel Halberstam’s ‘Of Power and Responsibility: The Political Morality of Federal Systems’⁹² was probably pioneering by its taking Germany, including the Weimar Republic, as an entity to compare the EU to, rather than the United States.⁹³ At the same time, the EU became interesting for scholars on the other side of the Atlantic too, since ‘the politics of integration were sufficiently peculiar to the European context as to allow for a depoliticized revival of classical debates’ in the US federalism.⁹⁴ Building on Halberstam, Robert Schütze’s *From Dual to Cooperative Federalism: The Changing Structure of European Law*,⁹⁵ originally defended in

⁸⁸ Armin von Bogdandy, ‘A Bird’s Eye View on the Science of European Law: Structures, Debates and Development Prospects of Basic Research on the Law of the European Union in a German Perspective (2000) 6 *European Law Journal* 208-238, 237-238.

⁸⁹ Signed in Rome on 29 October 2004; OJ of 18 July 2003, C 169/1.

⁹⁰ On the failed constitution see NW Barber, Maria Cahill and Richard Ekins (eds), *The Rise and Fall of the European Constitution* (Hart 2019).

⁹¹ Anne-Marie Slaughter, *A New World Order* (Princeton UP 2004) exemplifies the mood of the time. Critically see Stephen Gill and A. Claire Cutler (eds), *New Constitutionalism and World Order* (CUP 2014).

⁹² (2004) 90 *Virginia Law Review* 731-834.

⁹³ There was, however, Part III ‘The Federal Experience of Some Nation States: Selected Topics’ in ITL, containing chapter devoted to Australia, Canada, Germany and Switzerland.

⁹⁴ Daniela Caruso, ‘EU Law in U.S. Legal Academia’ (2011) 20 *Tulane Journal of International and Comparative Law* 175-201.

⁹⁵ (OUP 2009).

2005 as a PhD dissertation at the EUI,⁹⁶ was probably the most sophisticated contribution of this kind at the time.

Second, the Maastricht ruling brought from Germany to Europe another strand of constitutional theory: that of European Economic Constitution, understood then perhaps too narrowly as a set of rules of constitutional nature that govern economic relations and correspond to the ordoliberal ideology.⁹⁷ Only later did it give rise to a much more critical scholarship on the political economy of European constitutionalism, which abounded in reaction to the Euro-crisis. Christian Joerges, between 1998 and 2007 the Professor of European Economic Law at the EUI,⁹⁸ has brought this perspective to Florence.⁹⁹ Miguel Poiaras Maduro's *We the Court*,¹⁰⁰ defended at the EUI in 1996 was probably the most influential PhD dissertation written under Joerges' supervision.

Third, constitutional pluralism was gaining more and more influence, especially as it seemed to offer a plausible account of legal and constitutional normativity in the absence of a clear hierarchy between different legal orders and increasingly porous borders between them. Neil Walker, between 2000 and 2008 Professor of European Law at the EUI,¹⁰¹ was the key figure that helped to turn constitutional pluralism from a "dissenting" position into an orthodoxy – although this was certainly at the price of analytical precision.¹⁰² How else can one explain that it was called (with a slight hyperbole) 'the only party membership card which [would] guarantee a seat at the high tables of the public law professoriate',¹⁰³ and that the President of the Court of Justice Koen Lenaerts pledged allegiance to it?¹⁰⁴

Close to the theory of constitutional pluralism came the concept of multilevel constitutionalism, introduced, also in response to the Maastricht ruling, by Ingolf Pernice.¹⁰⁵ The English translation does not capture what Pernice wanted to achieve: the German term *Verfassungsbund*

⁹⁶ The thesis had a slightly different title – 'From dual to cooperative federalism: the changing structure of the legislative function in the European Union': see <https://cadmus.eui.eu/handle/1814/4783> (24 July 2023).

⁹⁷ See Werner Bonefeld, *The Strong State and the Free Economy* (Rowman & Littlefield International 2017).

⁹⁸ For a compendium of Joerges' most important writings in several fields see his *Conflict and Transformation: Essays on European Law and Policy* (Hart 2022).

⁹⁹ See particularly his 'What is left of the European economic constitution? A melancholic eulogy' (2005) 30 *European Law Review* 461-489, delivered as the introductory lecture of the Academy of European Law - Session on European Union Law, EUI July 5, 2004.

¹⁰⁰ *We The Court. The European Court of Justice and the European Economic Constitution: A Critical Reading of Article 30 of the EC Treaty* (Hart 1998). For a contemporary critical re-evaluation of the book see Robert Schütze, 'Judicial majoritarianism revisited: "we, the other court"?' (2018) 43 *European Law Review* 269-280.

¹⁰¹ Walker's key contributions in this respect are 'The Idea of Constitutional Pluralism' (2002) 65 *Modern Law Review* 317-359 and 'Constitutional Pluralism Revisited' (2016) 22 *European Law Journal* 333-355.

¹⁰² Important in this respect was not only a conference that took place at the University of Oxford on 20-21 March 2009 (that gave rise to Avbelj and Komárek, n 78), but also a debate among Neil Walker, Miguel Maduro, Mattias Kumm (who were identified as "pluralist" by the organisers), and Julio Baquero Cruz, who formulated a strong critique of constitutional pluralism in 'The Legacy of the Maastricht-Urteil and the Pluralist Movement' (2008) 14 *European Law Journal* 389-422. The transcript of the debate was published as Matej Avbelj and Jan Komárek, 'Four visions of constitutional pluralism: symposium transcript' (2008) 2 *European Journal of Legal Studies* 325-370.

¹⁰³ Joseph HH Weiler, 'Prologue: global and pluralist constitutionalism – some doubts' in Gráinne de Búrca and Joseph HH Weiler (eds), *The Worlds of European Constitutionalism* (CUP 2012), 8-18, 8.

¹⁰⁴ Koen Lenaerts, 'Democracy, Constitutional Pluralism and the Court of Justice of the European Union' in Luuk van Middelaar and Philippe Van Parijs (eds), *After the Storm: How to Save Democracy in Europe* (Tiel: Lannoo 2015), 123-137.

¹⁰⁵ See (in English) Ingolf Pernice, 'Multilevel Constitutionalism and the Treaty of Amsterdam: European Constitution-Making Revisited?' (1999) 36 *Common Market Law Review* 703-750.

put emphasis on how national and the EU's constitutions are compounded into one, "composite" constitution of Europe, which comprises both levels and do not require the state to exist. *Staatenverbund*, the term coined by the Maastricht ruling's reporting judge Paul Kirchhof, stressed the state and statehood: something the EU was not intended to become or acquire even by its proponents.¹⁰⁶ Multilevel constitutionalism thus tapped into two important debates of the time: constitutional pluralism and also 'constitutionalism beyond the state'.¹⁰⁷

The four approaches mentioned above (federalism, economic constitutionalism, constitutional pluralism and multilevel constitutionalism) did not have a clear master-philosophy behind them. However, as the field of EU constitutional theory had become more and more autonomous from legal and political practice, some scholars sought to apply various political and legal philosophies in the context of the EU. Mattias Kumm thus developed a theory of "best fit"¹⁰⁸ that was clearly inspired by Ronald Dworkin's *Law's Empire*,¹⁰⁹ Armin von Bogdandy built his theory of European constitutional law on Jürgen Habermas' philosophy,¹¹⁰ and Ulrich Haltern, (to be sure, much less known in comparison to those already mentioned)¹¹¹ was inspired by Paul Kahn's cultural study of law.¹¹²

Finally, apart from the wide-ranging, structural theories of European integration, there have been theoretically ambitious attempts to re-think some core concepts of constitutional law and theory to make them fit for the new, "post-national" era: citizenship,¹¹³ fundamental rights,¹¹⁴ democracy,¹¹⁵ sovereignty¹¹⁶ adjudication and judicial legitimacy,¹¹⁷ or constitutional legitimacy as such.¹¹⁸

As already mentioned, the EUI has been at the centre of these debates and it may therefore appear surprising that one person who chiefly contributed to this role, Joseph Weiler, was among some very few academics who opposed the project to establish a formal written "constitution".¹¹⁹ After the failure of the Constitutional Treaty he was joined by many more –

¹⁰⁶ For a remarkably clear exposition of the German debate and the intellectual history of the concept see Franz C Mayer, Mattias Wendel, 'Multilevel Constitutionalism and Constitutional Pluralism: *Querelle Allemande* or *Querelle d'Allemand*?' in Avbelj and Komárek, n 78, 127-151, especially at 128-132.

¹⁰⁷ On this notion see particularly Joseph HH Weiler and Marlene Wind (eds), *European Constitutionalism beyond the State* (CUP 2003) and

¹⁰⁸ Mattias Kumm, 'The Jurisprudence of Constitutional Conflict: Constitutional Supremacy in Europe before and after the Constitutional Treaty' (2005) 11 *European Law Journal* 262-307.

¹⁰⁹ Belknap Press 1986.

¹¹⁰ See n 83.

¹¹¹ See particularly 'Pathos and Patina: The Failure and Promise of Constitutionalism in the European Imagination' (2003) 9 *European Law Journal* 14-44.

¹¹² Paul W Kahn, *The Cultural Study of Law: Reconstructing Legal Scholarship* (University of Chicago Press 1999) and other works by Kahn cited in fn. 19 of Haltern, n 111.

¹¹³ Out of many see e.g. Richard Bellamy, Dario Castiglione and Jo Shaw (eds), *Making European Citizens: Civic Inclusion in a Transnational Context* (Palgrave Macmillan 2006).

¹¹⁴ Philip Alston (ed), *The EU and Human Rights* (OUP 1999).

¹¹⁵ For example James Bohman, *Democracy across Borders. From Dêmos to Dêmoi* (Polity 2007).

¹¹⁶ Neil Walker (ed), *Sovereignty in Transition* (Hart 2003).

¹¹⁷ Mitchel de S.-O.-l'E. Lasser, *Judicial Deliberations: A Comparative Analysis of Transparency and Legitimacy* (OUP 2004) or Aida Torres Pérez, *Conflicts of Rights. A Theory of Supranational Adjudication* (OUP 2009).

¹¹⁸ Jan-Werner Müller, *Constitutional Patriotism* (Princeton UP 2006).

¹¹⁹ See 'On the power of the Word: Europe's constitutional iconography' (2005) 3 *International Journal of Constitutional Law* 173-190.

but this part of our story does not concern constitutional theory as a scholarly endeavour and relates more to the role of constitutional scholars in politics, which we cannot explore here.¹²⁰

5. Constitutional Theory without the Constitution, 2005 until?¹²¹

The EU had only recently recovered from the failure to establish a written constitution, when the Eurocrisis – and the many other crises of (and in) Europe outbroke.¹²² While before the Eurocrisis there had been rather few (if any) critical theories of European constitutional law, this last period has seen an ever-growing number of them. At the same time, however, there have been still other scholars who sought to provide a “constructive” theory of EU constitutionalism or some of its aspects.¹²³ For the first time, probably, theorisation about legal disintegration also appeared, albeit in the field of social sciences¹²⁴ – and was soon warned against by a constitutional scholar.¹²⁵

Another important aspect of this last period concerns the disappearance of constitutionalism from the EU’s politics. The EU – again – has been managed by smart lawyers-engineers, who instead of producing big ideas wanted to provide “solutions”. Some of the theories of EU constitutional law then focused on the crisis management and the consequences it had for the legitimacy of the EU.

The important strands of constitutional theory that emerged after Maastricht found their successors, providing further sophistication to original theories. Signe Larsen’s *The Constitutional Theory of the Federation and the European Union*¹²⁶ went beyond comparative analysis to provide a theory inspired by several political and legal philosophers, especially Carl Schmitt’s theory of the Bund.¹²⁷

Schmitt, and the debate among the German constitutional scholars before the collapse of the Weimar republic in 1933 (particularly Hermann Heller) were important for another contribution, which went far beyond “economic constitutionalism” promoted by Christian Joerges in the earlier period. Michael Wilkinson’s *Authoritarian Liberalism and the Transformation of Modern Europe*¹²⁸ is probably the first EU constitutional theory that takes

¹²⁰ See Jan Komárek, ‘Freedom and Power of European Constitutional Scholarship’ (2021) 17 *European Constitutional Law Review* 422-441.

¹²¹ Compared to the foregoing sections of this chapter, this one is more descriptive in the attempt to map the ever-increasing field of EU constitutional theory and its main strands; inevitably, it is selective and to some extent reflects the preferences of the chapter’s author. Apologies to all colleagues who feel unjustly omitted: they can revenge in the most accessible way to academics: by ignoring the author in their work.

¹²² On the Eurocrisis see Kaarlo Tuori and Klaus Tuori, *The Eurozone Crisis: A Constitutional Analysis* (CUP 2014).

¹²³ See e.g. Floris de Witte, *Justice in the EU. The Emergence of Transnational Solidarity* (OUP 2015).

¹²⁴ Hans Vollaard, ‘Explaining European Disintegration’ (2014) 52 *Journal of Common Market Studies* 1142-1159.

¹²⁵ Franz Mayer, ‘Of Blind Men, Elephants and European Disintegration – What could and what should legal academics do against the “disintegration” of Europe?’ *Verfassungsblog* of 26 March 2015, <https://verfassungsblog.de/von-blinden-maennern-und-elfanten-was-kann-und-sollte-die-rechtswissenschaft-gegen-die-desintegration-europas-tun/> (4 August 2023).

¹²⁶ OUP 2021.

¹²⁷ Larsen, n 126, 13, fn 16. One must note at this place, however, that similarly ambitious project was written and defended at the EUI in 2009 by Matej Avbelj; the key argument of his thesis ‘Theory of European Bund’ was published as ‘Theory of European Union’ 36 *European Law Review* 818-836.

¹²⁸ OUP 2021.

political economy seriously – and besides Schmitt and other Weimar scholars brings Karl Marx (and Marxism) into the debate on EU constitutionalism.¹²⁹

While to some extent Larsen's, and certainly Wilkinson's book can be read as contributions to the critical theory of EU constitutional law, the new literature on constitutional pluralism produced in this last period was the opposite, seeking to provide justification for what the EU is (and a normative ambition for what it should become).¹³⁰ Once a somewhat dissenting position constitutional pluralism has become mainstream, despite some ill-targeted attacks by scholars-activists, who saw the theory as complicit in the EU's legal disintegration (represented by the increasing "disobedience" – or disagreement with the ECJ - of national constitutional courts).¹³¹

Another critical approach to EU constitutionalism was brought by the Austrian scholar (who spent significant time in the United States) Alexander Somek. First in his *Individualism*¹³² and later *The Cosmopolitan Constitution*¹³³ Somek challenged some central assumptions made by those who wanted to provide theories of legitimacy capable of justifying supranational arrangements brought about by the EU.¹³⁴ Somek's critical work on European integration started to appear already before the Eurocrisis¹³⁵ and in this sense was much advanced compared to most what had been produced in the field at the time. The reference to cosmopolitanism in the title of the second-mentioned book is in no way its embrace: Somek is deeply critical of administrative rationality and intersubjective passivity involved in such type of constitutionalism, which abandoned its core ambition: emancipation. The book concludes: 'No emancipation is possible without political action. To this end, the nation state appears today more indispensable than ever before.'¹³⁶ To be sure, Somek is not nostalgic after some form of self-sufficient nationalism; at the same time, he is deeply sceptical of constitutionalism's possibility to overcome a bounded political unit – the state.

Paul Linden-Retek takes an opposite view to Somek in his *Postnational constitutionalism*.¹³⁷ His view that 'the great emancipatory vision of European postnationalism, ..., is the possibility to institutionalize the non-sovereign character of constitutional judgement and political agency' cannot be more opposite to Somek's diagnosis and one may wonder whether the two will engage in a direct debate at some point.¹³⁸

¹²⁹ See also Maria Tzanakopoulou, *Reclaiming Constitutionalism: Democracy, Power and the State* (Hart 2018).

¹³⁰ See especially Klemen Jaklic, *Constitutional Pluralism in the EU* (OUP 2014) and Matej Avbelj, *The European Union under Transnational Law: A Pluralist Appraisal* (Hart 2018).

¹³¹ See . Daniel Kelemen, Piet Eeckhout, Federico Fabbrini, Laurent Pech, Renáta Uitz, 'National Courts Cannot Override CJEU Judgments: A Joint Statement in Defense of the EU Legal Order' *Verfassungsblog* of 26 May 2020, <https://verfassungsblog.de/national-courts-cannot-override-cjeu-judgments/> (20 August 2020).

¹³² *Individualism. An essay on the authority of the European Union* (OUP 2008).

¹³³ OUP 2014.

¹³⁴ See particularly 'The argument from transnational effects I: Representing outsiders through freedom of movement' (2010) 16 *European Law Journal* 315-344 and 'The argument from transnational effects II: Establishing transnational democracy' (2010) 16 *European Law Journal* 375-395.

¹³⁵ See e.g. 'A Constitution for Antidiscrimination: Exploring the Vanguard Moment of Community Law' (1999) *European Law Journal* 243-271; 'Equality and Constitutional Indeterminacy. An Interpretative Perspective on the European Economic Constitution' (2001) 7 *European Law Journal* 171-195 – work that culminated in another important book by Somek, *Engineering Equality: An Essay on European Anti-discrimination Law* (OUP 2011).

¹³⁶ Somek, n 133, 283.

¹³⁷ *Postnational constitutionalism: Europe and the time of law* (OUP 2023).

¹³⁸ See Linden-Retek's critique of Somek at *Ibid*, 46-49.

The last important contribution to EU constitutional theory, which seeks to re-think some key assumptions of constitutional theory in the light of European integration experience is Turkuler Isiksel's *Europe's Functional Constitution*.¹³⁹ Thinking about constitutional authority, Isiksel adds a third element to those usually recognized by other theories: a system of government must not only be democratic while respecting individual rights (the well-known dilemma of constitutional democracies); it must also 'realize those commitments *and* enable effective government'.¹⁴⁰ In Isiksel's view, the EU is unique in how this third principle of constitutional authority dominates over the other two, which remain relatively underdeveloped. Moreover, the EU's functionalism focuses on just one goal: delivering a market, other objectives and competences notwithstanding. The following passage embodies the spirit and message of Isiksel's book and deserves quoting at length:

While most observers tend to see the expansion of the EU's tasks as evidence that it has grown beyond its economic origins, however, I contend that the reverse is true: the expansion of the EU's operations has engendered the colonization of ever greater swathes of public policy by institutions designed primarily to create and govern a supranational market. ... The result is the refraction of key principles of political legitimacy such as democracy, equality, and solidarity, and of key institutions such as representation, citizenship, and constitutionalism through the prism of economic union.¹⁴¹

Isiksel believes that the EU is capable of some 'reflective readjustment' to overcome this market-centredness. Others remain skeptical.¹⁴²

All theoretical works mentioned thus far need to be distinguished from those that continue to apply the state template to the European Union. Dieter Grimm represents this approach.¹⁴³ Not in the way of suggesting that the EU should become a state, but rather in measuring the legitimacy of its governing structures by the state-based template.¹⁴⁴

In a way, these approaches have in common the rejection of the constitutional character of the EU with another set of theories, which we mention for the sake of completeness, as they conceptualize EU legal order in non-constitutional terms: either as an extension of the national administrative state¹⁴⁵ or as an advanced international experiment.¹⁴⁶ I mention them here only in passing, as they do not, as stated, represent *constitutional* theories of the EU, but theories about its *legal* nature.

6. Conclusion

This chapter could not provide an exhaustive and systematic account of EU constitutional theory – given the number of publications in various languages, this would require a whole

¹³⁹ Turkuler Isiksel, *Europe's Functional Constitution: A Theory of Constitutionalism beyond the State* (OUP 2016).

¹⁴⁰ Isiksel, n 139, 74.

¹⁴¹ *Ibid*, 19.

¹⁴² See my review article, Jan Komárek: 'Rethinking constitutionalism and democracy . . . again?' (2019) 17 *International Journal of Constitutional Law* 992–1005.

¹⁴³ Dieter Grimm, *The Constitution of European Democracy* (OUP 2017).

¹⁴⁴ See Komárek, n 142 and also Walker, n 2 (for the same analysis).

¹⁴⁵ See e.g. Peter L. Lindseth, *Power and Legitimacy: Reconciling Europe and the Nation-State* (OUP 2010).

¹⁴⁶ See Bruno De Witte, 'The European Union as an advanced international law experiment' in De Búrca and Weiler, n 103, 19-56.

handbook of its own and probably a team of authors well-versed in different constitutional cultures of the EU member states. Instead, it sought to provide a comprehensible narrative, which puts the growing literature in legal history and sociology into a new perspective, while trying to learn as much as possible from them. An “internal” intellectual history of EU constitutional law and theory is an endeavour that requires a closer attention to be paid to legal *concepts* and their *use* by legal scholars advancing various theoretical claims. This chapter could be but an introduction to such account.